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Research Article

**THE COMPARISON OF SUBLAY AND ONLAY TECHNIQUE
FOR REPAIRING VENTRAL HERNIA IN TERMS OF
POSTOPERATIVE DRAIN REMOVAL TIME AND WOUND
INFECTION**¹Dr Mudassar Ali, ²Dr Hamza Bashir, ³Dr Zara Aslam¹Quaid e Azam Medical College Bahawalpur, ²Sheikh Zaid Medical college Rahim Yar Khan,
³CMH Lahore Medical College.**Article Received:** March 2019**Accepted:** April 2019**Published:** May 2019**Abstract:**

Objective: The comparison of sublay and onlay technique for repairing ventral hernia in terms of postoperative drain removal time and wound infection. This randomized controlled study was held from June to December 2018. Sublay took place in Services Hospital Lahore. The hernia patients were divided into two equal groups A and B. Group A was subjected to onlay technique while latter were given sublay repair technique. After 1 year of index surgery operative repair was performed. This time period was necessary for scar maturation. After experiment, data was analyzed using SPSS-23 and time taken for drain removal of both the groups was compared.

Results: There were 100 patients, half in each group. Mean age of patients present in group A was 40.30±0.23 days. The condition in terms of wound infection was also important.

Conclusion: For repairing ventral hernia, sublay hernia repair was a good alternative to onlay repair of ventral hernia.

Keywords: ventral hernia, sublay, onlay.

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INTRODUCTION:

Hernia is abnormal exit of sac covered organ or part of organ through a naturally or artificially formed opening. For hernia repair Jorgen through knowledge about internal structure of body and skilled expertise is required. Ventral hernia can also be called as anterior abdominal wall hernias, umbilical, paraumbilical, epigastric, spigelian and incisional hernias are included in it [1]. Incidence of ventral hernia is estimated to be 15-20% and prosthetic meshes are being used for incisional ventral hernia repair. With its advent, recurrence rate has decreased up to 10%. More recently, techniques have been developed to lace prosthetic mesh intraperitoneally [2]. Due to this, recurrence rate has dropped less than 5%. Outcomes are influenced by the position of reinforcement by the position of reinforcement. Only onlay and sublay are the two techniques for operation that

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

This controlled study was made at surgical Department of Jinnah Medical Karachi. The program was started from June to December 2018 with the consent of institute ethics committee. Written agreement was taken from all patients undergoing surgery for abdominal hernia. Patients were selected using non-probability consecutive sampling technique. Size of sample was calculated using WHO 'sample size calculator. Level of significance was 5% and power of test 90%. For making the following calculation drainage for onlay group was taken as 7.4 ± 1.7 days and in sublay group as 4.5 ± 1.1 days. Patients of both genders were included. Their age group was 28-25 years. They had epigastric, Para umbilical or incisional ventral abdominal hernia. Patients with strangulation removed from the experiment.

The sample was divided into 2 groups. In group A, sublay repair was given to patients whereas in group B, patients were subjected to onlay repair. Relevant

RESULTS:

There were total 100 patients, 50% in each group. Mean age in group A was 40.30 ± 4.52 years and 39.12 ± 4.58 years in group B mean WHR was taken as 0.84 ± 0.06 and 0.84 ± 0.06 and 0.78 ± 0.05 respectively in both groups. In overall result 18(18%)

are mostly used. However, it is still unclear that which technique is more effective [3].

In onlay repair mesh is placed b/w the subcutaneous tissues of abdominal wall and anterior rectus sheath. However in sublay repair peritoneal plane is made b/w rectus muscle and posterior rectus sheath. In sublay repair, to prevent chance of infection post-operation, the mesh is laid deep. A study made by Eker HH, proved that wound infection was 5% in open repair and 4% in laparoscopic repair. The main reason for getting surgical case is the improvement of quality of life related to health and to get relief from distress [4]. This was made for comparison of sublay versus onlay meshplasty in terms of its effect on drainage time after operating and wound infection in the final result.

Investigation and clinical examination was given to the patients. For incisional hernia complications faced in previous surgery and the data was used. After 1 year of index surgery, operative repair was started. This time was required for maturation. Thealing of senior trained surgeons performed various operative techniques of sublay and onlay mesh repair. Data was arranged in tabular form and co-existing and co-morbid conditions and predisposing risk factors were identified. Before operation, patients waist-hip ratio was measured to estimate the presence of fat abdominal wall. Women with $HHR > 0.85$ and men with $WHR > 0.90$ were defined as obese. According to classification data was analyzed using SPSS-23 mean \pm standard deviation was used for qualitative data like age, WH ratio and drain removal time for qualitative data like hypertension, diabetes mellitus, obesity, gender and wound infection, frequency and percentage was calculated. Chi-square test was used for comparison of wound infection and T-test was for comparing drainage time b/w groups. $P < 0.05$ was taken as reference.

Patients had hypertension, 8(8%) had diabetes mellitus and 18(18%) were obese (table-i). Besides there were 28(56%) and 27(54%) females in A and B group respectively. 14(28%) patients suffered from wound infection in group A and 6(12%) in group B. Mean drain removal time in group A was 4.40 ± 1.53 days and 3.06 ± 0.23 days in group B.

Table-1: characteristics of study variables (n=100).

	Onlay (n=50)	sublay (n=50)	total (n=100)
Age	40.30±4.52	39.12±4.58	39.71±4.57
WH ratio	0.84±0.06	0.78±0.05	0.81±0.06
Hypertension			
Yes	11(22%)	7(14%)	18(18%)
No	39(78%)	43(86%)	82(82%)
Diabetes Millitus			
Yes	6(12%)	2(4%)	8(8%)
No	44(88%)	48(96%)	92(92%)
Obesity			
Yes	5(10%)	13(26%)	18(18%)
No	45(90%)	37(74%)	82(82%)

Table-2: comparison of wound infection & Mean drain removal time between both groups.

Technique	Wound infection		P-value	Technique	Drain Removal Time(Mean±SD)	P-value
	Yes	No				
Onlay	14	36		Onlay	4.40±1.53	
Sublay	6	44	0.04*	Subly	3.06±0.23	0.01*
Total	20	80				

DISCUSSION:

After an abdominal operation the interior abdominal was contained both spontaneously and most commonly incisional hernia. About 2-11% of all abdominal operations resulted in incisional hernia. These days tension free prosthetic mesh is being used. Its use has decreased the risks of recurrence to a negligible level. Primary tissue repairs can be used for closing small hernias less than 2.5cm in diameter [5]. However in case of larger hernia only the use of tissue repair can increase the risks of recurrence from up to 30-50%. The recurrence of hernia is a source of stress for a person as it disturbs the thinking of patient related to result of repair and it also causes financial burden on them. These circumstances have led to the acceptance of mesh repair. A study has proved that use of mesh has increased from 34.2% in 1987 to 65.5% in 1999.

Mesh placement in preoperational, retro-muscular

sublay position overlapping the hernia defect in all directions was first time used in late 1980s. The betterment of sublay technique has required the recurrence rates and gave better results [6]. This has made it a best cure for ventral hernia. A research has given different induction rates among various mesh materials. No difference has been recorded between onlay and sublay repairs. Once when the bacteria's reach alloplastic material, it becomes difficult for immune system to target them. It is highly applicable for micro porous meshes, but to a lesser extent, also for meshes with larger pores that allow immune cells to enter into them. One randomized clinical test recently proved that meshes with low molecular weight can prevent some specifically determined infections at implantation site.

It was also noticed that patients who received fresh mesh material experienced less pain and mesh awareness. Wound infection can be defined as an

attach of pathogenic microorganisms and other multiplication of wound site [7]. This invasion may result in tissue injury and a possibility of aiding disease by various cellular or toxic mechanisms. In mesh hernioplasty, it is a terrifying problem sometimes it becomes so severe that it becomes compulsory to remove the mesh. But fortunately, mostly small wounds are observed in the research [8]. According to its risks of infections was 10% to 40%. At local level, many studies have recorded an infection rate of 5% to 10%. Which was comparatively less. One study recorded it as 12% while the other reported the wound infection as 6%. In our experiment wound infection observed in sublay was 12% and in onlay was 28%. Sublay mesh repair can be considered as a best alternative to applied to all types of ventral hernia.

study. Indian J Surg. 2007;69:95-8.

CONCLUSION:

There were 100 patients, half in each group. Mean age of patients present in group A was 40.30 ± 0.23 days. The condition in terms of wound infection was also important. Better and effective technique for repairing ventral hernia was sublay mesh repair. After operation the time complication regarding drainage and wound infection was much low.

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